

A Study of Bangladeshi Youth Opportunity and Social Capital: A case of Facebook Use

Md Abdur Razzak, Md Serajul Islam & Jinzhang Jiang

Abstract

This study inspects Facebook habit on Bangladeshi youths and navigation to their facilitations. In extension, it also investigates whether Facebook usage influence to hunt new knowledge and capacity building such as social bonding, social capital and acquiring new skills and opportunities. Realistic data was composed from 312 Bangladeshi youth Facebook users through a questionnaire survey. It was observed that educational status is subjective on Facebook use while gender has no significant relationship advancing youth opportunities by the Facebook use. The study outcome also pointed up that there is a constructive bonding between youth opportunities and Facebook usage i.e. mostly active users modeling prospect youths related to opportunity search and social capital. The study also steers a positive browsing manual to the Bangladeshi youth Face book users who wish to see the Facebook as a "Savebook" that is really needed for the South Asian socio-economic context.

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1. Introduction

We are living the age of information, first coined this term by Manuel Castell in his famous three volume work (Hafez, 2007). Social Media (SM) is nothing except continuing social relations (Fuchs, 2017). It is very warm perception to receive the simple and straight jacket meaning of social media from social scholar Safko. He explained it as “Social Media is a media, we use to be social” (Safko, 2010). Youth can be framed after the children age (Grow et al., 2008). The age group from 15 to 24 is accepted as “youth” age in any United Nations mandate member countries. Young people are tremendously changing in the modern societies. Even, they have the capacity to transform the worst of everything to make wonderful to the earth. These changing attitudes directly affect their social bonding relationship such as family, friends and relevant networks (Furlong & Cartmel, 2006). They are the real hero to dream for the society as well as for the own country even to the globe. Three western scholar framed the youth age very innovative way (Donald, Anderson, & Spry, 2010). The youth eyes and mind always awesome to find new solutions through their creativity and power of imagination (Alves, 2011). While they are full in prospective and futuristic, they turn themselves in a societal asset. James Coleman and Robert Putman of U.S.A with Pierre Bourdieu from France are forefront spokes personnel of social capital. Bridging and linking capital within the groups are essential to promote for betterment of the social advancement (Helve & Bynner, 2007). Broadly, social networks add special value to the youth and inspire to achieve mutual goal (Baron, Field, & Schuller, 2000). Social capital is a communal issue that open wider window of individual benefit is the key from Hanifan definition. On the other hand, social capital is defined by OECD as “networks together with shared norms, values and understandings that facilitate co-operation within or among groups.

Currently, social media especially Facebook has drawn the attentions of all spheres of lives, specially the prime-movers (the young) of the nations. The Seoul of South Korea, mobile phones (called handy phone) are used by the youths mainly in three specific issues such as (1) sharing documents, (2) editing and (3) upload their lives onto social networking sites (SNS) but the youths of Japan and China are using in diversified way (Hjorth, 2008). The availability of web-based devices have given the opportunity to interact, interconnect and diffuse innovation in the field of health, agriculture, education, export-import as well as creating opportunities for job seekers, integration of people into the labor market and empowering communities, and paving the way to community mobilization. Bangladesh is a small South Asian country with huge population. Facebook is the most popular social media in Bangladesh (Soron, 2015). Statistic of the year 2013 showed the Facebook users in Bangladesh as 3, 724,800 where the Facebook users are 4% (13 to 15), 9% (16 to 17), 49% (18 to 24), 29% (24 to 34), 6% (35 to 44) and rest of the 3% is over 44 years old (Bristy, 2016). Other study raveled that 25% was the teenager out of 73% of Bangladeshi Facebook users (Ahmed, Hossain, & Haque, 2012). Ultimately, new media technology like face book are widely used in the society according to the age and education (Couldry, Hepp, & Krotz, 2009). This study will consider overall well being, youth employment (job opportunities), acquiring information for increasing knowledge, civic engagement, entertainment and cultural diversity as a concept of youth opportunities.

1.1 Research Questions (RQ)

The following research questions answered on A Study of Bangladeshi youth opportunities and social capital: A case of Facebook use.

RQ1: What are the motivations of Bangladeshi youth to use Facebook as a prominent social media?

RQ2: Is the Facebook open any opportunities for Bangladeshi youth?

1.2 Literature Review

Social media is a souvenir to the youth. It enables and enlightens them to contribute for the society and the humanity. More advanced way, Facebook is counting as a mirror of latest trend of current youth's motivation. It is helping Bangladeshi youth to keep things in control. Being a web-based tool, Facebook is equipping and digitizing the youth community in engaging various activities even their individual benefits. Youths are the symbol of power and prosperity in every society. They are the only force to sacrifice for mankind. Youths are the real hero of the society. Their cultures represent the specific social culture. Pujolar defined it nicely. He noted that youth cultures are the reflection of social practices (Pujolar, 2013). Youths have the adaptive ability to think modern fashion and styles. Youths are reshaping the society in every single minute throughout the globe. They are really the symbol of imagination, creativity, positive and socio-economic changer (Donald et al., 2010). The future belongs to the young. They live on hope and turn into the future leader. They can plan, act and demonstrate all aspects of development which are needful to the society particularly where they live. Youths are the pillar to understand social need (Kim, 2008). Moreover, youths are the life blood of any nation. They have confidence and hard-working manner that lead to gear up the society. Social media is sliding this gear up mission by connecting the technology and the youth spirit. In addition, youths are constructive a new horizon of using new media platform for reshaping new landscape of new media literacy (Ito et al., 2009).

Facebook is a safe book where users save their like, comments, states, life-style and updates information for others as a character of virtual custody. But the initial Facebook spotlight was little bit difference. It was created in February 2004 by Mark Zuckerberg, Dustin Moskovitz and Chris Hughes as a site for Harvard students only. Shortly after, it expanded to any college student with a .edu e-mail account. Between fall 2005 and Fall 2006, Facebook expanded to high school networks, first, work networks, later, and, eventually, to Internet users in general (Valenzuela, Park, & Kee, 2008). Smith and his colleague have drawn attention about the relation of Facebook and its contribution to the society (Treadaway & Smith, 2012). They have opined that Facebook acts as a "social plug in". It means society is vibrating through Facebook. Facebook page is like a famous restaurant where people visit to taste. After getting flavor, they announce their identity which is difference from others. Ultimately, Facebook users are smart, affluent and internet-savvy people (Holzner, 2008). It always concerns about the wide range of services for its potential users. Social scientist informed that Facebook is providing servicing in seventy-five languages (Gerodimos, 2010). Positively, it is also giving opportunity to post, share, call and transaction in the virtual world. Ultimately, Facebook is leading the "Virtual world" (Haydon, Dunay, & Krueger, 2012). It is also the powerhouse of academic resources (Jacobson, 2011). In a broader sense, it carries the users top to bottom to continue social souvenir. Actually, Facebook draw the social graph (Russell, 2013).

Social capital is the emerging researching topic in social science from the last few decade (Lin, 2017). The French scholar Bourdieu has attracted most scholars by giving his famous opinion on social capital. He noted as "the actuator potential resources which are linked to a durable network of more or less institutionalized relationships of mutual acquaintance or recognition" (Bourdieu, 2011). Society and social capital are two wings of a bird. Youths are

the power; Facebook is the interacting tool and social capital is personal boost up. Individuals may access social capital resources such as useful information, personal relationships, opportunities for professional development (Phulari et al., 2010). On a community level, social capital may foster social cohesion through "the norms of reciprocity and trustworthiness" that flow from social networks (Gamham, 2000). Facebook is not only connecting people but also stepping revolutionary effort for creating digital enterprises (Turban et al., 2017). It is also the technological gift to the education. Youths are getting several benefits by using its multiple features in the field of education. Chaffey has investigated that Facebook is technology friendly and users are enjoying its numerous services (Chaffey, 2007). It is not a miracle to open a Facebook account and share information only; it will be sensation episode while youths are using it for turning any innovative activities.

2. Research method and material

a) As a Qualitative research, it is used an extensive documents of scholarly journals & articles, research reports, books, government statements and websites with relevant topics to explore Facebook interaction by Bangladeshi youth, opportunities and social capital. Furthermore, a survey has been conducted to examine face book interactions by youth in keeping mind of social capital and described youth opportunities.

b) Statistical tools for data analysis used in the study

c) Univariate analysis: Descriptive Statistics (Frequency distribution)

d) Vicariate analysis: χ^2 -test for test the association between two variables.

Chi-Square Test for Independence

The Chi-square test of independence is used to determine if there is a significant relationship between two nominal (categorical) variables.

Suppose that Variable A has r levels, and Variable B has c levels. The null hypothesis states that knowing the level of Variable A does not help you predict the level of Variable B. That is, the variables are independent.

H_0 : Variable A and Variable B are independent.

H_a : Variable A and Variable B are not independent.

The alternative hypothesis is that knowing the level of Variable A *can* help to predict the level of Variable B.

The analysis plan describes how to use sample data to accept or reject the null hypothesis. The plan should specify the following elements.

- Significance level. Often, researchers choose significance levels equal to 0.01, 0.05, or 0.10; but any value between 0 and 1 can be used.
- Test method. Use the chi-square test for independence to determine whether there is a significant relationship between two categorical variables.

e) Regression Analysis for Multiple analyses

In statistics, linear regression is a linear approach to modeling the relationship between a response variable and one or more explanatory variables. The case of one explanatory variable is called simple linear regression. For more than one explanatory variable, the process is called multiple linear regressions.

Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) procedure performs linear regression on the selected dataset. This fits a linear model of the form

$$Y = b_0 + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + \dots + b_k X_k + e$$

Where Y is the dependent variable (response) and $X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k$ are the independent variables (predictors) and e is random error. $b_0, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_k$ are known as the regression coefficients, which have to be estimated from the data. The multiple linear regression chooses regression coefficients so as to minimize the difference between predicted values and actual values. Linear regression is performed either to predict the response variable based on the predictor variables, or to study the relationship between the response variable and predictor variables.

f) Presentation of results

- Figures: Bar diagram, Segmented bar diagram, Pie-chart, doughnut plot, Radar Plot, Bubble plot, etc.
- Tables: Cross tables to show the association between two variables.

g) Computer software for data analysis

Computer software, SPSS has been used for data analysis. In the present study, SPSS of its version **22** has been used to enter survey data to software, preprocess and analyze them with univariate and bivariate statistical techniques. Statistical tests are also performed with this software. Finally, data analysis outputs are presented in tabular and graphical form with SPSS. Another data processing computer tool, Microsoft Excel under Microsoft Office 2007 has been used to draw figures and do other necessary calculations.

3.0 Results and discussion

Currently, social media especially Facebook has drawn the attentions of all spheres of lives, especially the young in Bangladesh. Therefore, the use of Facebook has been increasing dramatically here like other parts of the world. There are multi-dimensional impacts of this social media in the society as well as individual lives of the users. The study was targeted to find the factors which are significantly impacting our social and individual life for using Facebook as a social media especially, socio-demographic factors, social capitals and social opportunities for the youths, and to see the pattern of association among these factors. Socio-demographic factors of such as: Sex, Age, Current engagement, Study level, marital status and Religion are very much related with use and pattern of use of this social media. At the same time, impact of Facebook to different group of people is different in the society.

Perception and experience of users about Facebook are not equal to all. To some people, it is advantageous and helps them to make their life easy and make them more social. However, few people have adverse experience and perception on this social media. Social Capital factors like: believe on social life, participation to local community as a volunteer before and after joining to Facebook, trustworthiness of Facebook people, helpfulness of Facebook friends, visiting neighbor house, participation in local organization or club, feeling as a part of global community, feeling as a part of team player, visit local community with your family, going market for shopping, helpfulness of Facebook friends on decision making, help in case of emergency loan, remove loneliness, belongingness to larger community might have association with Facebook use. Youths are getting opportunities from Facebook use in different ways. They got educational materials and information to be trained up and groom them up to be fit for next future profession. They also get some clues or ideas to be involved into some economic activities such as starting a new business or to be a successful entrepreneur. They also get knowledge and information about their housing, sensation about their family and parenthood and finally, about health and life-style. As a tool for data collection, Likert Scale has been used in the questionnaire to get a scaled response from the participants to the study for giving information from their own experience and perceptions.

Frequency distributions of the variables have been presented with different types of graphs and charts (Bar chart, Pie chart, Radar plot, Doughnut chart, Bubble chart, etc). Chi-square (χ^2) test was performed to assess the strength of association between the variables. Cross-tables and multiple bar chart and segmented bar chart have been used for showing the associations. To reach to a decision of acceptance or rejection of hypothesis 5 percent level of significance has been considered. Here the null hypothesis to be tested is that there is no association between the two variables and respective alternative hypothesis is there is an association between them. Regression Analysis has been applied in the study to show the individual factor's contribution on Facebook use. Here the directions of association (positive or negative) are also presented with the sign before the coefficients for the variable in the regression equations. The significance of the regression equations has been tested as well with 5 percent level of significance.

3.1 Socio-demographic information of respondents: -

Among the socio-demographic factors of respondents, Sex, Age, Current engagement, Study level, marital status and Religion have been considered in the study

3.1.1 Sex

Facebook use pattern is not same among male and female. Similarly, impacts of Facebook do not work on female and male social and individual life equally.

Figure 1 Sex of respondents

Among the respondents 55 percent are male and 45 percent are female. There is respondent from transgender although there is an option in the questionnaire.

3.1.2 Age

Facebook is used by all age of people nowadays even though young people are more active in Facebook.

Figure 2 Age of respondents

Most of the respondents (66 percent) participated in the study are between the age 20 to 24 years. About one third of them are from 15 to 19 years old.

3.1.3 Study level

Educational qualification is one of the strong background factors to study Facebook use and social cohesion.

Figure 3 Respondent's educational qualification

Most of the respondents completed their under graduate study (42.3 percent) which is followed by post graduate study (25 percent). About 20 percent of them have completed their higher secondary level of education. Approximately 13 percent of the respondents have secondary school level education.

3.2 Association of Facebook use and sex of respondents

Gender is one of the socio-demographic factors which vary with different social phenomena. Choice, preference, taste, interest on Facebook is a matter to be assessed in any study. The following cross-table along with the Chi-square (χ^2) test of independence shows the association of Facebook use and sex of respondents.

Table 1 Association of Facebook use and sex of respondents

Use of Facebook per-day	Sex of respondents		Total
	Male	Female	
I do not visit everyday	11 (50.0%)	11 (50.0%)	22 (100.0%)
1-30 minutes	55 (1.9%)	51 (48.1%)	106 (100.0%)
31-60 minutes	46 (56.1%)	36 (43.9%)	82 (100.0%)
60-90 minutes	27 (58.7%)	19 (41.3%)	46 (100.0%)
90-120 minutes	20 (64.5%)	11 (35.5%)	31 (100.0%)
More than 120 minutes	13 (52.0%)	12 (48.0%)	25 (100.0%)
Total	172 (55.1%)	140 (44.9%)	312 (100.0%)
Pearson Chi-Square value-2.155, df-5, p-value= 0.827			

It is evident from above cross table and the χ^2 test that there is no association between Facebook use and sex of respondents participated in the study. That means both male and female use Facebook.

3.3 Regression model of Facebook use and socio-demographic factors of the users

Some socio-demographic factors of respondents are related with Facebook use (FBU) per day and some are not. Now we are going to find the influencing factors which have impact on Facebook use through regression analysis. Fitted regression model is:

$$FBU = 2.437 + 0.739 * \text{age} - 0.898 * \text{st} + 0.117 * \text{edu}$$

(R²=0.147, Adjusted R²=0.139, Significance value or p-value=0.000)

It is evident from the regression equation that age and educational status of the respondents are positively associated with Facebook use. However, their current status, such as currently study or not, have negative relation. That means respondents who are currently studying spend more time on Facebook use than those who are not engaged otherwise currently. The model is overall significant (p<0.05) at 5 percent level of significance. Coefficient of multiple determinations (R²) expressed how the variables in the right sight of the equation influence the variable in the left. Here, age, current engagement and education of the respondents express about 15% of the variation in Facebook use (FBU).

3.4 Facebook Usage: -

Having Facebook account, assistance during Facebook account opening, duration and frequency of visiting or using Facebook per day, Facebook friends, well connected friends, number of followers, access to Facebook profile, device use for Facebook by respondents are discussed in this section. In addition to these, respondents' opinions regarding pros and cons of using Facebook, its usefulness for individual development and social cohesion are investigated in this part the study.

3.4.1 Active Facebook Account

Figure 4 having an active Facebook account

Some 98 percent of the respondents have active Facebook account and remaining 2 percent of them do not have active Facebook account.

3.4.2 Frequency of visiting Facebook

Figure 5 Frequency of visiting Facebook page

Majority of the respondents (83.3 percent) respondents reply that they use Facebook daily. About 10 percent of them said that they use this social media once every few day. More than 3 percent of them use this once a week. More than one and half percent more people use

Facebook once every few weeks and remaining approximately 2 percent of them use this modern social connectivity means less than once a month.

3.4.3 Time spent on Facebook per day

How much time a person spends for using Facebook in a day is more important than how many times he or she use it per day. Though out the study, this variable is used as the accounting factor for involvement to Facebook use of a person.

Figure 6 Time spent on Facebook per day

Slightly more than one third of the respondents (34 percent) use Facebook 1-30 minutes, which is followed by half an hour to one hour which accounts for about 26 percent. After that, the percentage of respondents gradually decreases as time increases. At last only about 7 percent of them do not visit Facebook every day.

3.4.4 Use of smart phone as device for using Facebook

Figure 7 Using Facebook in the smart phones

Exactly 87 percent of the respondents use Facebook in their smart mobile phone. Remaining 13 percent use this most popular social media in their computer.

3.5 Regression model of Facebook use and respondents' opinion on its advantages and disadvantages

All factors of respondents are not equally related to their pattern and timing of Facebook use (FBU). In order to find the individual factor's contribution on Facebook use, regression analysis has been done. From the analysis, the fitted regression model is:

$$\text{FBU} = 2.21 + 0.175 * \text{wastetime} + 0.152 * \text{connect} - 0.099 \text{chat}$$

$$(R^2 = 0.281, \text{ Adjusted } R^2 = 0.201, \text{ Significance value} = 0.000)$$

The above regression model shows that respondent’s opinion on Face booking as a waste of time, it helps to connect with friends and family is positively associated with Facebook use. However, their perception about it as Facebook chat enrich users have negative have negative relation. That means respondents who agree, moderately or strongly that chatting through Facebook use it less. The model is overall significant ($p < 0.05$) at 5 percent level of significance. Coefficient of multiple determinations (R^2) expressed how the variables in the right sight of the equation influence the variable in the left. Here, Opinion on whether Facebook visit a waste of time through Likert scale, Opinion on whether Facebook helps to connect with friends and family, Opinion on whether Facebook chat enrich users express about 28% of the variation in Facebook use (FBU).

3.6 Social Capital: -

It is assumed that most popular social media, Facebook and social capitals are related to each other. In order to find out the factors of social capitals which have direct association, some of them have been incorporated in the present research. They are: Believe on Social Life, Participation to local community as a volunteer before and after joining to Facebook, Trustworthiness of Facebook people, Helpfulness of Facebook friends, Visiting neithbour house, Participation in local organization or club, Feeling as a part of global community, Feeling as a part of team player, Visit local community with your family, Going market for shopping, Helpfulness of Facebook friends on decision making, Help in case of emergency loan, Remove loneliness and Belongingness to larger community.

3.7 Believe on Social Life

Figure 8 Believe on social life

Majority of the respondents (26.6 percent) strongly agree that they believe on social life. Approximately 22 percent of them moderately agree, about 15 percent slightly agree that that they believe on social life. However, very close to 18 percent of the respondents slightly, 11 percent moderately and 8.7 percent strongly disagree that they believe on social life.

3.8 Participation to local community as a volunteer before and after joining to Facebook

Figure 9 Participation to local community as a volunteer before and after joining to Facebook

A comparative picture of respondents in participation to local community as a volunteer before and after joining to Facebook has been presented in the following bar chart. From the above figure a significant impact of Facebook use can be observed. Before use Facebook, percentage of respondents who never or rarely or even sometimes participate to local community as a volunteer was higher. On the contrary, after using Facebook respondents often, very often or always participate to local community as a volunteer.

3.9 Helpfulness of Facebook friends

A great portion of respondents slightly disagree (27 percent), moderately disagree (31 percent) and strongly disagree (15 percent) that several people in their Facebook friends are ready to help as per need. On the other hand, 15 percent respondents slightly agree, 7 percent moderately agree and only 5 percent respondents strongly agree that Facebook friends are ready to help you as per need.

Figure 10 Helpfulness to Facebook friends

3.10 Visiting neighbors' house after communicating in Facebook

Approximately 25 percent respondent strongly, about 18 percent moderately and 22 percent slightly disagree that they visit neighbors' house after communicating in Facebook. On the contrary, 12.8 percent slightly, 12.5 percent moderately and about 10 percent respondents strongly agree that they visit neighbors' house after communicating in Facebook.

Figure 11 visiting neighbor's house after using Facebook

3.11 Participation in local organization or club

Majority of the respondents give their opinion indifferently regarding this question. About 25 percent respondents slightly disagree that Facebook is enabling them as an active member in a local organization or club such as sport, local event, social club, social trip & charity club). About 20 percent of them moderately disagree and about 13 percent strongly disagree this. However, near about 22 percent of the respondent slightly, 11.2 percent moderately and 9.3

percent strongly agree that Facebook enable them as an active member in a local organization or club.

Figure 12 Participation in local organization or club after joining Facebook

3.12 Helpfulness of Facebook friends on decision making

Two third of the respondents disagree (slightly-25 percent, moderately-25 percent and strongly-16 percent) that they got their Facebook friends helpful in case of decision making. Remaining one third of them agree this (slightly-19.2 percent, moderately-10.9 percent and strongly-3.8 percent).

Figure 13 Helpfulness toward Facebook friends on decision making

3.13 Regression model of Facebook use and factors relating to Social Capital

All factors of respondents are not equally related to their pattern and timing of Facebook use (FBU). In order to find the individual factor's contribution on Facebook use, regression analysis has been done. From the analysis, the fitted regression model is:

$$FBU = 2.632 + 0.011 * \text{before} + 0.121 * \text{after} - 0.068 * \text{trust} - 0.191 * \text{help} + 0.068 * \text{club} + 0.010 * \text{team} - 0.015 * \text{shopping} + 0.144 * \text{community}$$

$$(R^2 = 0.089, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = 0.065, \text{Significance value} = 0.000)$$

The above regression model shows relation of Facebook use with respondents opinion through Likert Scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree on participation to local community as a volunteer before joining to Facebook (before), participation to local community as a volunteer after joining to Facebook (after), trustworthiness of Facebook people (trust), helpfulness of Facebook friends (help), participation in local organization or club (club), feeling as a part of team player (team) and going market for shopping (shopping). Here participation to local community as a volunteer before joining to Facebook (before),

participation to local community as a volunteer after joining to Facebook (after), trustworthiness of Facebook people (trust), participation in local organization or club (club), feeling as a part of team player (team) and belongingness to larger community (community) are negatively associated with Facebook use. However, helpfulness of Facebook friends (help) and going market for shopping (shopping) are negatively associated with Facebook use per day. The model is overall significant ($p < 0.05$) at 5 percent level of significance. Coefficient of multiple determinations (R^2), expressed how the variables in the right side of the equation influence the variable in the left.

3.14 Youth Opportunities: -

Youth Opportunities have been characterized by Education & Training, Economic activities, Employment opportunities, Urban, Rural and Migration, Housing, Family and Parenthood and Health, Life-style and Drug are considered in the present study.

3.14.1 Association between Facebook use and Youth Opportunities

It is very necessary to see the association between Facebook use and life related factors of individuals such as, education and training, economic phenomenon, employment opportunities, place of residence and migration, housing, family and parenthood, health and life-style. Some users agree that Facebook chat enrich users, but some do not. The time spent on Facebook is slightly associated to the users opinion on whether Facebook chat enrich users or not.

Table 2 Association of Facebook use with the user's opinion whether it helps or enrich

Use of Facebook per-day	Facebook users' opinion						Total
	Strongly Disagree	Moderately disagree	Slightly disagree	Slightly agree	Moderately agree	Strongly Agree	
I do not visit everyday	2 9.1%	6 27.3%	3 13.6%	2 9.1%	5 22.7%	4 18.2%	22 100.0%
1-30 minutes	8 7.5%	7 6.6%	16 15.1%	23 21.7%	14 13.2%	38 35.8%	106 100.0%
31-60 minutes	7 8.5%	9 11.0%	18 22.0%	15 18.3%	9 11.0%	24 29.3%	82 100.0%
60-90 minutes	4 8.7%	8 17.4%	9 19.6%	10 21.7%	6 13.0%	9 19.6%	46 100.0%
90-120 minutes	0 0.0%	6 19.4%	6 19.4%	11 35.5%	3 9.7%	5 16.1%	31 100.0%
More than 120 minutes	5 20.0%	3 12.0%	7 28.0%	7 28.0%	2 8.0%	1 4.0%	25 100.0%
Total	26 8.3%	39 12.5%	59 18.9%	68 21.8%	39 12.5%	81 26.0%	312 100.0%
Pearson Chi-Square value-37.632, df-25, p-value= 0.045							

3.15 Regression model of Facebook use and respondents' opinion on its advantages and disadvantages

All factors of respondents are not equally related to their pattern and timing of Facebook use (FBU). In order to find the individual factor's contribution on Facebook use, regression analysis has been done. From the analysis, the fitted regression model is:

$$FBU = 2.21 + 0.175 * wastetime + 0.152 * connect - 0.099 chat$$

(R²=0.281, Adjusted R²=0.201, Significance value=0.000)

The above regression model shows that respondent’s opinion on Facebooking as a waste of time, it helps to connect with friends and family are positively associated with Facebook use. However, their perception about it as Facebook chat enrich users have negative have negative relation. That means respondents who agree, moderately or strongly that chatting through Facebook use it less. The model is overall significant (p<0.05) at 5 percent level of significance. Coefficient of multiple determinations (R²) expresses how the variables in the right sight of the equation that influences the variable in the left. Here, Opinion on whether Facebook visit a waste of time through Likert scale, Opinion on whether Facebook helps to connect with friends and family, Opinion on whether Facebook chat enrich users express about 28% of the variation in Facebook use (FBU).

3.16 Association between Facebook use and increasing competency for future plan

Figure 14 Association between Facebook use and increasing competencies for future plan

Pearson Chi-Square value-14.953, df-25, p-value= 0.942

Facebook use does not increase competency for future plan, and it is evident from the above segmented bar chart (p>0.09).

3.17 between Facebook use and Boosting Knowledge and Skills

Figure 15 Association between Facebook use and boosting knowledge

A significant association can be observed between Facebook use and users opinion on it helps to boosting knowledge and skills (Pearson Chi-Square value-44.71, df-25, p-value= 0.009<0.05) at 5 percent level of significance.

3.18 Association between Facebook use and Finding information to be an entrepreneur

Considering even 0 percent error, we can say that there is a strong association between Facebook use and respondents' opining in case of finding information to be an entrepreneur (Pearson Chi-Square value-89.856, df-25, p-value= 0.00).

Figure 16 Association between Facebook use and finding information to be an entrepreneur

3.19 Regression model of Facebook use and factors relating to youth opportunities

In order to find the individual factor's contribution on Facebook use, regression analysis has been done. From the analysis, the fitted regression model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{FBU} = & 2.024 + 0.072 * \text{knowledge} - 0.034 * \text{business} + 0.374 * \text{entrepreneur} + 0.010 * \text{job} \\
 & - 0.016 * \text{hometown} - 0.022 * \text{urban} - 0.022 * \text{migration} - 0.021 * \text{decoration} \\
 & + 0.147 * \text{family} - 0.144 * \text{parents} - 0.026 * \text{drugs}
 \end{aligned}$$

(R²=0.206, Adjusted R²=0.177, Significance value=0.00)

The above regression model shows relation of Facebook use with respondents opinion through Likert Scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree on Boosting knowledge and skills (knowledge), Getting positive direction to start a new business (business), Finding information to be an entrepreneur (entrepreneur), Receiving job hunting news (job) and Connecting closely with family members (family) are positive. On the other hand, Alerting on home town news (hometown), Facilitating information of urban living (urban), Updating pathway of migration (migration), Modernizing tips to decorate houses, Informing the way to

honor parent (parents) and Informing the risks of drugs (drugs) have negative relation with Facebook use per day. The model is overall significant ($p < 0.05$) at 5 percent level of significance. Coefficient of multiple determinations (R^2) expressed how the variables in the right side of the equation influence the variable in the left. Here, about 20 percent of variation in Facebook use can be expressed by factors mentioned above in the right side of the model.

3.20 Impacts of Facebook:-

In order to assess the impacts of Facebook on individual and social life, Facebook enable to contribute to the society, Facebook open the door of passive engagement, Facebook is the power house of news and information and Facebook provide the access of real time social interaction have been considered in the study.

3.21 Facebook enables to contribute to the society

The horizontal bar chart below shows the frequency distribution of respondents on the statement Facebook enables to contribute to the society in Likerts Scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

Figure 17 Facebook enables to contribute its user to the society

Approximately 7.5 percent of the respondents strongly disagree that Facebook enables to contribute to the society. As opinion in favour of this statement goes on from strongly disagree towards moderately agree, the number of respondents also increases (26 percent) even though number of respondents decreases to 16 percent who strongly agree.

3.22 Facebook open the door of passive engagement

Frequency distribution of the respondents on their opinions from strongly disagree to strongly agree on Likerts scale about the statement Facebook opens the door of passive engagement are presented in the bar chart below:

Figure 18 Facebook open the door of passive engagement

3.23 Facebook is the power house of news and information

The following doughnut chart shows the frequency distribution of the respondents on their opinions on the statement Facebook is the power house of news and information.

Figure 19 Facebook is the power house of news and information

The highest number of respondents (27 percent) strongly agrees that Facebook is the power house of news and information which is followed by moderately agree 26 percent. Number of respondents decrease as opinions more towards strongly disagree (5 percent).

3.24 Facebook provide the access of real time social interaction

Figure 20 Facebook provide the access of real time social interaction

About one fourth of the respondents (23.7 percent) strongly agree that Facebook provide the access of real time social interaction. Almost equal percentage of respondents (about 20 percent) moderately and slightly agree this. Exactly 16 percent of them slightly disagree, 12.2 percent moderately disagree and finally 7.4 percent strongly disagree that Facebook provide the access of real time social interaction.

3.25 Regression model of Facebook use on its impacting factors

It has already found that some factors of respondents are related with Facebook use (FBU) per day and some are not. Now we are going to find the influencing factors which have impact on Facebook use through regression analysis. Fitted regression model is:

$$\text{FBU} = 3.331 + 0.150 * \text{power} - 0.216 * \text{provide}$$

$$(R^2 = 0.052, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = 0.046, \text{Significance value} = 0.00)$$

The above regression model shows relation of Facebook use with respondents opinion through Likert Scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree on its role as the power house of news and information (power) is positive. On the contrary, its role to provide access to real time social interaction has negative relation with Facebook use per day. The model is significant ($p < 0.05$) at 5 percent level of significance. Coefficient of multiple determinations (R^2) expressed how the variables in the right side of the equation influence the variable in the left. Here, about 5.2 percent of variation in Facebook use can be expressed by factors mentioned above in the right side of the model.

4.0 CONCLUSION

The present study has attempted to find the factors which have association Facebook Use with social capital and youth opportunity related factors. At first the socio-demographic information of respondents has been studied. Next, social capital related factors have also been investigated with their association with Facebook use. After that, factors which are pertinent with youth opportunities have been studied as well. Finally, some factors which have impact on Facebook have been examined with their relationship with Facebook use. All these analyses have been done based on respondents' six level opinions from strongly disagree to strongly agree in Likerts Scale.

4.1 Facebook Usage: -

Respondents express their opinions on the pros and cons of using Facebook. Here, opinions on whether Facebook visit a waste of time, opinion on whether Facebook helps to connect with friends and family and opinion on whether Facebook chat enrich users have association with Facebook use. On the contrary, opinion on whether Facebook helps to connect various social networking sites do no have any relation with duration of Facebook use per day.

4.2 Social Capital: -

Facebook users' perception and practice on social capital and their association with Facebook use have been studied and presented here. Users' participation to local community as a volunteer before and after joining to Facebook, Trustworthiness of Facebook people, helpfulness of Facebook friends, and participation in local organization or club, feeling as a part of team player, going market for shopping and belongingness to larger community are significantly related to Facebook use. On the contrary, Facebook users believe on Social Life, visiting neighbor house, feeling as a part of global community, visit local community with your family, helpfulness of Facebook friends on decision making, help in case of emergency loan and remove loneliness are found irrelevant here.

4.3 Youth Opportunities: -

Youth Opportunity related factors have been investigated in the current research. Analysis shows that Boosting Knowledge and Skills, Getting positive direction to start a new business, Finding information to be an entrepreneur, Receiving job hunting news, Alerting on home town news, Facilitating information of urban living, Updating pathway of migration, Connecting closely with family members, Informing the way to honor parent and Informing the risks of drugs are significantly associated with Facebook use. On the other hand, Helping users' learning needs, Increasing competency for future plan, Economic activities of

respondents, Supporting to make an impressive Resume/CV, Urban, Rural and Migration, Keeping inform on Rent a house details, modernizing tips to decorate houses, Awakening the preventive measure of various diseases and Mastering new life-style do not have any relationship with Facebook use.

4.4 Impacts of Facebook: -

Impact of Facebook on individuals' lives or their social lives has studied as well in the current study. Here it is found that Face book's role as the power house of news and information and its role to provide access to real time social interaction are associated with Facebook use per day. However, its contribution to the society and its impact on passive engagement are not significantly associated with Facebook use.

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References

- Ahmed, S., Hossain, M., & Haque, M. (2012). Usage of facebook: Bangladesh perspective. *Mahbulul, Usage of Facebook: Bangladesh Perspective (May 15, 2012)*.
- Alves, R. (2011). *Tomorrow's child: Imagination, creativity, and the rebirth of culture*: Wipf and Stock Publishers.
- Baron, S., Field, J., & Schuller, T. (2000). *Social capital: Critical perspectives*: OUP Oxford.
- Bourdieu, P. (2011). The forms of capital.(1986). *Cultural theory: An anthology*, 1, 81-93.
- Bristy, J. F. (2016). Factors affecting the adoption of social network: A study of Facebook users in Bangladesh. *The Journal of Social Media in Society*, 5(1), 137-159.
- Chaffey, D. (2007). *E-business and E-commerce Management: Strategy, Implementation and Practice*: Pearson Education.
- Couldry, N., Hepp, A., & Krotz, F. (2009). *Media events in a global age*: Routledge.
- Donald, S. H., Anderson, T. D., & Spry, D. (2010). *Youth, society and mobile media in Asia*: Routledge.
- Fuchs, C. (2017). *Social media: A critical introduction*: Sage.
- Furlong, A., & Cartmel, F. (2006). *Young people and social change*: McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
- Gamham, N. (2000). *Emancipation, the media and modernity. Arguments about the*.
- Gerodimos, R. (2010). *New media, new citizens: the terms and conditions of online youth civic engagement*. Bournemouth University.
- Grow, H. M., Saelens, B. E., Kerr, J., Durant, N. H., Norman, G. J., & Sallis, J. F. (2008). Where are youth active? Roles of proximity, active transport, and built environment. *Medicine & Science in Sports & Exercise*, 40(12), 2071-2079.
- Hafez, K. (2007). *The myth of media globalization*: Polity.
- Haydon, J., Dunay, P., & Krueger, R. (2012). *Facebook marketing for dummies*: John Wiley & Sons.
- Helve, H., & Bynner, J. (2007). *Youth and social capital*: Tufnell Press London.
- Hjorth, L. (2008). *Mobile media in the Asia-Pacific: Gender and the art of being mobile*: Routledge.
- Holzner, S. (2008). *Facebook marketing: leverage social media to grow your business*: Pearson Education.

- Ito, M., Horst, H. A., Bittanti, M., Stephenson, B. H., Lange, P. G., Pascoe, C., . . . Mahendran, D. (2009). *Living and learning with new media: Summary of findings from the Digital Youth Project*: MIT Press.
- Jacobson, T. B. (2011). Facebook as a library tool: Perceived vs. actual use. *College & Research Libraries*, 72(1), 79-90.
- Kim, Y. (2008). *Media consumption and everyday life in Asia*: Routledge.
- Lin, N. (2017). Building a network theory of social capital Social capital (pp. 3-28): Routledge.
- Phulari, S., Khamitkar, S., Deshmukh, N., Bhalchandra, P., Lokhande, S., & Shinde, A. (2010). Understanding formulation of social capital in online social network sites (SNS). arXiv preprint arXiv:1002.1201.
- Pujolar, J. (2013). *Gender, heteroglossia and power: A sociolinguistic study of youth culture (Vol. 4)*: Walter de Gruyter.
- Russell, M. A. (2013). *Mining the Social Web: Data Mining Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Google+, GitHub, and More: " O'Reilly Media, Inc."*.
- Safko, L. (2010). *The social media bible: tactics, tools, and strategies for business success*: John Wiley & Sons.
- Soron, T. (2015). Successful management of Facebook addiction in Bangladesh: A case report. *Journal of Psychiatry*, 18(2), 1000247.
- Treadaway, C., & Smith, M. (2012). *Facebook marketing: An hour a day*: John Wiley & Sons.
- Turban, E., Outland, J., King, D., Lee, J. K., Liang, T.-P., & Turban, D. C. (2017). *Electronic commerce 2018: a managerial and social networks perspective*: Springer.
- Valenzuela, S., Park, N., & Kee, K. F. (2008). Lessons from Facebook: The effect of social network sites on college students' social capital. Paper presented at the 9th International Symposium on Online Journalism.

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